

Cruise log SR2406-SR2408
April 25th-May 22nd 2024
Amy Maas

Funding:

OCE-2419287: Ship Operations for Research Vessel SALLY RIDE

OCE-2127538, OCE-2127524, OCE-2127299: Collaborative Research: Metabolic habitat barriers imposed on tropical diel vertical migrators

April 26th (SR2406)

Worked on writing and TA projects in the morning. Discovered that we have time to work during transit so set up for a respiration run after lunch. Generated FSW from in-line seawater through Georig. Calibrated the high but not the low for all channels, set the temperature probes. Surface water was ~16C. HCl rinsed everything. Completed Tow 1 (no TDR as we did not have the software license, dive weight in the bottom, no hose clamp). The bucket got tipped and lots of critters ended up having to get rinsed back into water. Tons of large (5 cm) salps, Millions of tiny ones.

- Set up 3 biological replicates for the SalpPoopProject (SPP) with 2 salps per bucket in the 10C walk-in (start at 22:30).
- Set up four blocks of respiration at 15.5 degrees.

April 27th (SR2406)

Worked a bit on the tucker setup, did more writing and TA projects. Broke down SPP after lunch, broke down respiration after dinner. Amy got prednisone. Two tuna were caught on the back deck with trawl lines. Completed Tow 2 (yes TDR, no weight, added the hose clamp). Bucket came up with an air bubble, but the net seemed to filter in. Not many big things but a ton of small orange copepods.

- SalpPoopProject – breakdown (13:00) more than 10 fecal pellets per container. Preserved in -80 on filters for isotopes. Salps in cryovials.
- Respiration – breakdown (1730-1830) All clean curves, all alive. Animals in cryovials in -80 other than the two salps which are in falcons. Respiration – setup (2230) all four blocks at 15.5C

April 28th (SR2406)

Finished MOC setup (cod ends and a bit of net gluing). TA projects COMPLETE!!! Broke down respirations after lunch. 1 tuna caught in the morning. Completed Tow 3 (yes TDR, no weight, filled bucket with seawater before deployment. GORGEOUS.). While towing Pleuroncodes (squat lobster) at the surface, caught ~8. Nice happy Euphausiids (~6). Tons of POOP in the bucket (squat lobster I think).

- Respiration – breakdown. All alive. Saphorina did not breathe appreciably. Animals in cryovials in -80.

- Respiration – setup (2215) all four blocks at 20.6.

April 29th (SR2406)

MOC calibration. Two flow meters were mounted on the MOC. An old one and a new one. Deck test 1310, tow until xxx. Ran 1 km north at ~70 m, tripped the net, pulled the net up to 10 m, did a u-turn, put the net back down to ~60 m and ran the same line back. Reset the calibration for flow meter 1. The new flow meter seemed really sticky. Will keep an eye on it during the cruise. Lots of cool gelatinous organisms. 2 beroe ctenophores, tons of other purple banded ctenophores. MANY larger heteropods (Pterotrachea sp) that were laying eggs. A few pelagic octopus and a few pelagic TINY squidlings. Broke down respirations while the net was in the water (1 euphausiid mortality).

Tow
3:
tons
of

jelly. Siphonophore on the lines. Lots of inquisitive squid. EK80 showed bands at 60, 35, and 15-25. Net system seems solid.

- Respiration – breakdown. One euphausiid dead. Otherwise all good traces. Animals in cryovials in -80.
- Respiration – setup (2215) all four blocks at 20.6.

April 30th (SR2406)

Tucker test. Communications fine. No intention to close the net but we still caught a plethora of jelly critters. Thliptodon frozen for Brad. Wire flyer attempt. Great deployment but the instrument has errors. Broke down the respirations – everyone was alive. Hannah finished Lloyd’s pelican case. Big pterotrachea photographed and then put in swim tunnel. Dip net of Glaucus sp! Blue button as well. Going to try to respire them maybe?? Wire flier again! CTD is being spotty. Tow 5 easy peasy. Setting up a thecosome p-crit experiment. Turned on the second Lauda. One at 25 and one at 15. Some leakage – changed the hose – think everything is ok? AND! No thecosomes in the net. Bummer. Back to just doing

things at 25. FORGOT TO MOVE THE TEMP PROBE! The reading for two of the blocks needs to be corrected for temperature

- Respiration – breakdown. All good traces. Animals in cryovials in -80.
- Respiration – setup four blocks at 25.6

May 1st (SR2407) – La Paz!

Letting the respirations run. Brad respired some *Glaucus* (seemed to go well?). Noticed the temperature probe issue in the morning and switched it to the correct waterbath. Beach day. Chill.

May 2st (SR2407) – La Paz!

Letting the respirations run. Leg 1 people arrived. Revamp of the labs. Sail at 1600. Wire flier after dinner. Breaking down the respirations. Many things very dead.

May 3rd (SR2407) – Carmen Basin

CTD in the morning Jamie took water for metazoan metabarcoding and fluorescence. SCUBA divers successful. Corolla, *Diacavolinia*, *Creseis*, *Thliptodon* NON MIGRATORS! Respiring. All pteropods good idea for FPP experiments. Heteropods also non-migrators. Tucker went for like 1.5 h and was FULL of swimming myctophid, cyclothone, japtella, squid (*abraliopsis* and one dead pterygioteuthis), *beroe*, *hyalocylis*, euphausiids, shrimp and general gelatinous mess. Many organisms captured for respiration. Squid in the swim tunnel. Jamie preserved a ton in formalin for teaching. Wire flier is still having technical difficulties. Steaming to Guaymas. Wire flier did ok midnight to 6 am. There was an interesting midwater oxygen feature closer to carmen, not present closer to Guaymas.

May 4th (SR2407) – Guaymas Basin

8 AM dive, murkier, lots of jelly again. Similar community. Respiration broken down. Most pteropods had laid eggs, only one corolla was dead (so many egg masses). Eggs were set aside for joyful observation. MOCNESS at 11:00. Small snafu with the boat speed (stopped twice causing vertical velocities of -50 m/min), and the winch (went full stop at one point on the way down without need), but no broken nets or lost instrumentation on recover. Unfortunately Amy miscalculated the number of nets so the top net was 0-80 m. Also, the biomass here is MUCH more than BATS (oops), so there was way

more biomass than was functional. We decided to not make this the quantitative tow. Plan to make tonight 0-1000 and tomorrow 11:00 quantitative. Used this net to figure out what the communities are like. Found salps ~500-350. Found lots of ctenophores for the Haddock lab 250-160 (net 5 and 6). Haddock lab took tissue sample and returned animal to the whole preserved. Net 8 we preserved 1/2, net 9 we preserved 1/8 (it was nuts). Jamie took a number of organisms for photos and formalin from net 0. Wirefliier went for a dip before dinner to test out systems (seemed happier with less instruments plugged in last night). Net set up for night and now its nap time! Going to keep steaming up to the deeper basin for the MOC tonight.

Bioluminescence on the water tonight. Evening MOC was quantitative, but we had a double tripped net, thus the top is 0-80m. Analyzed it for biomass anyways. Net 8 was too abundant and we only kept half (thus the samples are quarters).

Collected two cryovials of *Lucicutia hulsemannae* and one cryovial of *Megacalanus* in RNA later for Leo. Meteor shower 4 am. Wirefliier until morning. Changing the second cold room to "warmer". Can't hit 15C. Closer to 17.

MOCNESS 2 (NIGHT)

MOCNESS 3 (DAY)

May 5th (SR2407) – Guaymas Basin

8 AM dive. One of the respirations fell over in the Lauda. Leaving it. The controls on unit 1 and 2 showed microbial but three and four looked clean. Ro and Sem broke down during Day MOC deployment, started filtering more water for the next few days. MOC 3 was successful. Checked the pteropod eggs – they are rotating and developed (both Diacria and Corolla). Tucker and Reeve both were successful. Our team was not quite ready to do respirations immediately. Got 14 and 20 ready and are setting up respirations.

May 6th (SR2407) – Guaymas Basin

Waves so no dive this morning. Tucker to lower

TRIP CONTROL						
Trip RSP	Date	Time	Pres	Net Angle	Flow Cnts	Volume
1			0.0	0.0	0	0.0
2	240505	191837	1000.0	24.8	265	2337.3
3	240505	194417	799.9	35.3	198	1577.9
4	240505	200932	549.5	33.5	259	2096.6
5	240505	202906	346.3	46.2	253	1840.1
6	240505	204025	249.9	47.0	136	922.8
7	240505	204535	199.7	52.3	68	450.6
8	240505	204936	159.6	49.2	54	366.1
9	240505	205543	79.2	50.9	88	593.5
10	240505	205823	39.7	50.4	39	259.9

oxycline ~900 m (#3). Respirations of fish.

Tucker from upper oxycline to surface (#4). Respiration of euphausiids (Ilyod's syringes). Tons of spectacular and unique organisms. Deep ostracod brooding babies. Many euphs with egg masses. Deep CTD cast (002). Started filtering water for Babbin. Peri pump tubing broke, replaced, started pumping again. Jamie took eDNA samples, Maas took samples for isotopes and microbial DNA. Some water was taken for filtering for photography. Steaming back towards where wire flier stuff happened last night. Reeve (008) successful but no salps. Surface tow (009). MOCNESS of horizontalness. Success.

NISKIN	DEPTH	Babbin	Doherty	Jamie	Jacob	Haddock	Notes
1	1650				X		
2	1650			X			
3	1000	X					Bottle 3.5 L
4	1000			X			
5	800			X			
6	800						
7	600			X			
8	600						
9	550		X				
10	550		X				
11	550	X					Bottle 2.8 L
12	400			X			
13	350		X				
14	350		X				
15	350					X	fsw
16	350					X	fsw
17	350					X	
18	200			X			
19	200	X					Bottle 2.6 L
20	100			X			
21	100	X					Bottle 3.5 L
22	20		X				
23	20			X			
24	20	X					Bottle 3.5 L

Net		Avg. oxygen	Min of oxygen	Max of oxygen	Avg. temp	Min temp	Max temp	Min depth	Max depth
0	D	1.616	0.113	5.350	14.4	9.5	23.2	-0.1	351.6
1	U	0.137	0.113	0.148	9.7	9.5	9.9	325.2	351.4
2	U	0.187	0.147	0.200	10.2	9.9	10.3	300.4	324.9
3	U	0.207	0.191	0.230	10.4	10.3	10.6	275.2	302.7
4	D	0.218	0.195	0.247	10.4	10.3	10.6	275.2	300.2
5	U	0.219	0.172	0.254	10.4	10.3	10.6	274.7	300.6
6	U	0.207	0.172	0.246	10.9	10.6	11.1	250.3	274.6
7	U	0.261	0.241	0.295	11.3	11.1	11.5	224.9	250.2
8	U	0.333	0.294	0.383	11.8	11.5	12.0	199.7	224.9
9	U	1.985	0.380	5.805	15.4	12.0	23.3	-0.2	199.7

TRIP CONTROL							
Trip	RSP	Date	Time	Pres	Net Angle	Flow Cnts	Volume
1	●	240507	054635	350.9	31.9	159	1328.9
2	●	240507	055314	324.9	38.7	51	397.7
3	●	240507	055920	300.4	39.3	51	386.9
4	●	240507	060833	275.3	41.4	79	608.2
5	●	240507	061501	300.2	40.5	48	374.1
6	●	240507	062133	274.7	41.0	57	444.0
7	●	240507	062629	250.2	41.9	47	355.9
8	●	240507	063101	224.9	42.6	44	332.1
9	●	240507	063541	199.7	42.9	46	342.4
10	●			0.0	0.0	0	0.0

May 7th (SR2407) – Guaymas Basin

Dive got salps. Day MOCNESS (m5) targeted scattering observed on ship acoustics. Double trip at bottom (noted response but not TRIP!? Advanced one motor and got a response. Should have said manual confirm). What is odd is that the “empty” net 1 came up with a fair amount of material?? Still, when I tripped net 9 (tried for 250 m there was no response and no angle change). Doing a back calculation of what the temp/pressure/oxygen was with the PRO file. Very interesting acoustic feature 400-350, then again 300. Lots of salps in the Tucker. Lloyd is very happy and there is fecal material for collection.

TRIP CONTROL							
Trip	RSP	Date	Time	Pres	Net Angle	Flow Cnts	Volume
1	●	240507	183425	423.8	50.6	245	1737.6
2	●	240507	184033	400.3	50.2	70	460.6
3	●	240507	184604	375.2	49.4	68	444.9
4	●	240507	185006	360.2	54.2	51	323.3
5	●	240507	185555	340.6	52.8	73	474.2
6	●	240507	185917	324.4	54.7	44	282.5
7	●	240507	190348	300.0	55.5	62	394.8
8	●	240507	190900	269.9	52.8	73	459.3
9	●	240507	191255	246.4	46.2	54	352.0
10	●			0.0	0.0	0	0.0

Trip Count	9	Flow Cnts	231	Flow Cnts2	0	Motor Volts	13.619
Confirms	10	VOL	2088.1	VOL 2	0.0	CTD Volts	14.137
Modem Data	231,0,9,10,0,1261,1309,0,0,0,3				FM2 Primary	CNF TIME	47.581
Modem Serial Port Status	●						

Strobe Box

Net	Avg. oxygen	Min of oxygen	Max of oxygen	Avg. temp	Min temp	Max temp	Min depth	Max depth
0	1.268	0.075	5.382	13.12	8.26	23.36	1	427
1	0.076	0.076	0.076	8.27	8.27	8.27	424	425
2	0.076	0.075	0.079	8.35	8.27	8.50	400	424
3	0.093	0.075	0.122	8.71	8.49	8.99	375	400
4	0.128	0.113	0.142	9.10	8.98	9.23	360	375
5	0.116	0.106	0.125	9.26	9.21	9.30	341	360
6	0.109	0.102	0.130	9.42	9.30	9.66	324	341
7	0.124	0.111	0.140	10.00	9.66	10.16	300	324
8	0.177	0.114	0.223	10.58	10.17	10.94	270	300
9	1.536	0.223	5.742	14.35	10.94	23.64	0	270

Wire flier had connection issues and did not sample the DVM. Went back in after sunset and is doing well. There is an interesting oxygen feature that appears to coincide with a backscatter layer. We decided to horizontally sample at 250 m. Successful but long tow. Plan to analyze will likely include only imaging the greater than 2000 fraction.

Net	Avg. oxygen	Min of oxygen	Max of oxygen	Avg. temp	Min temp	Max temp	Min depth	Max depth	Volume filtered
0	1.129	0.255	5.645	13.690	11.86	23.009	6	254.6	Lots
1	0.264	0.252	0.272	11.896	11.824	11.929	248.8	252.2	989.9
2	0.256	0.198	0.265	11.843	11.691	11.892	249.6	254.2	931.6
3	0.226	0.161	0.262	11.772	11.639	11.889	249.2	251.3	541.8
4	0.190	0.157	0.255	11.701	11.625	11.874	250.1	252.7	553.2
5	0.195	0.147	0.258	11.710	11.576	11.875	249	253.5	1504.7
6	0.153	0.089	0.202	11.624	11.537	11.676	248.3	252	3556.3
7	0.239	0.189	0.324	11.652	11.58	11.775	248.4	253.1	997.0
8	0.404	0.240	0.594	11.949	11.56	12.429	199.9	255.7	1021.9
9	1.973	0.477	5.700	15.744	12.419	23.293	-0.3	199.8	Lots

May 8th (SR2407) – Guaymas Basin
 Dive. Tucker trawl (first try it did not open, second try had some issues, then worked) to 1500mwo, 1350 actual depth, got the deep community. Cool orange chaetognaths. Set up respirations from the Tucker (Lucicutia, and amphipods). Started doing fecal pellet production experiments for Babbins (mollusca).

May 9th (SR2407) – Transited to Carmen

Arrived in Carmen with some Wireflyer. WAYYYY more backscatter on the EK80 system. Two bands from 450-400 and again around 300. Blue water dive got another salp (new species!) and some mating Thliptodon. Different species of heteropod (*Carinaria cithara*??). Tucker to 450. Closed prematurely? Cod end cold and full of euphausiids + myctophids + shrimp, front of the net FULL of ctenophores, got some salps. Amy started crustacea fecal pellet experiments in copepotties. Respirations started with diverse set of things. Wireflyer technical difficulties ongoing. Dip netted some blue buttons and floaty snails.

Group photo. Hannah worked on an R code for the new Firinging stinky software output. Got the Wireflyer functional around 2000. Noticed the midwater CTD bulge again. Made plans for optimal sampling leg 2 to look at midwater features coherent with acoustics info. Might need to respire some midwater critters.

5/10/2024 (SR2407) – Carmen

Wireflyer completed and a plan was hatched to sample odd midwater oxygen feature that reflected backscatter. Reeve net to 150 mwo, probably only got to 80. No salps, lots euphausiia, ostracods, baby pteropods, rhincalanus, new gymnosomes (Steve photographed *Pneumoderma* sp). Respirations with chaetognatha, heteropods, massive shrimp, rhincalanus. MOCNESS (7) to sample midwater feature 330. Mostly successful, why are 7 and 8 as they are? Seem backwards (volume filtered and community). I think we switched the cod ends at the last minute. Blue water dive collected chain salp, doliolid, siph, heteropods. Tucker to 275 scattering layer: tons of salps, baby myctophids, ostractods, some ctenophores. Tucker to 350 scattering layer: pterygeouteuthis squid, abraleopsis squid, leptocephalus, big myctophids, pluroncodes (!!), salps (small). Wireflyer went in for a little day tow.

TRIP CONTROL							
	Trip RSP	Date	Time	Pres	Net Angle	Flow Cnts	Volume
1	●●	240510	102632	330.9	54.3	520	3145.1
2	●●	240510	104215	330.0	53.4	207	1244.3
3	●●	240510	105750	329.8	55.5	214	1254.1
4	●●	240510	111929	330.0	54.4	294	1748.4
5	●●	240510	112725	330.5	55.6	107	643.9
6	●●	240510	113242	331.1	54.9	71	424.7
7	●●	240510	114016	329.4	56.5	103	632.2
8	●●	240510	115457	331.0	52.5	179	1181.7
9	●●	240510	120152	329.4	47.3	71	506.3
10	●●	240510	122855	-0.3	6.9	395	2556.6

Net	Avg. oxygen	Min of oxygen	Max of oxygen	Avg. temp	Min temp	Max temp	Min depth	Max depth	Volume filtered
0	0.762	0.243	5.176	12.453	10.880	23.956	2.6	340.2	Lots

1	0.379	0.360	0.399	11.053	10.985	11.086	328.5	331.4	1244.3
2	0.373	0.323	0.389	10.987	10.927	11.018	329.5	331.7	1254.1
3	0.283	0.207	0.381	10.965	10.890	11.074	328.8	330.8	1748.4
4	0.187	0.154	0.214	10.988	10.948	11.014	329	330.4	643.9
5	0.153	0.133	0.189	10.931	10.906	10.957	330.2	331	424.7
6	0.140	0.109	0.200	10.924	10.877	10.994	329.2	332.3	632.2
7	0.151	0.106	0.205	10.825	10.608	10.984	329.2	354.1	1181.7
8	0.135	0.130	0.143	10.963	10.928	11.073	329.5	334.6	506.3
9	1.085	0.143	5.434	14.239	11.086	23.863	-0.4	329.4	Lots

5/11/2024 (SR2407) – La Paz

Port! Drop off 4, pick up 4! Reeve 2200 to 450 mwo. Some salps, set up respiration with random organisms. Surface capture of flying fish and misc. Went through a slick of ??? Red colored, took a video. Did a dip net after we passed the worst of it and got BILLIONS of larvaceans. Microscope video of that. Second Reeve to 20 m. Not that exciting. Steam to Carmen overnight

5/12/2024 (SR2408) – Carmen

Dive successful. Failed wireflyer deployment. Missed communication between tugger, a-frame and deck command resulted in overstretching of the tugger line, which then broke. The flyer fell from the top shiv down onto the clump shattering the fiberglass and scaring everyone. No injuries. Instruments all seem to be fine, no internal damage to the canisters. Everything taken apart and reassembled. Gluing of the fiberglass back together through much of the day to allow for later redeploy without the tuggers. In the meanwhile, did the first LOKI deployment. Slow to figure out slip/tag location, but smooth operation. Sent to 300, up as slow as possible (not as slow as they would like, but it works). Deep CTD (bottom depth 2611.5). Collecting for eDNA, isotopes, Babbins, ethanol (Brad). Medical emergency in the crew so returning to port. Setting up respirations with remaining dive animals. VERY cute video of the copepods.

NISKIN	DEPTH	Babbins	Doherty	Jamie	Seibel	Notes
1	2591					
2	2591			X		
3	1998.13					
4	1998.16			X		
5	1000	no				
6	1000			X		
7	800					Did not work
8	800			X		
9	600		X			
10	600		X			
11	600			X	X	
12	600	X				
13	360			X		
14	320					
15	320		X			
16	320		X			
17	320			X	X	
18	200	X				
19	200			X		
20	102			X	X	
21	102	X				
22	24		X			
23	24	X		X		
24	6			X		

5/13/2024 (SR2408) – La Paz

Dip test of the wire flyer at the dock. All instruments functional! 2100 Reeve net while transiting. Respirations with random animals (bottom depth was only 260m as we were still close to port so the community was very different).

5/14/2024 (SR2408) – Carmen

Wireflyer success. EK system crapped out half way through but there is an interesting oxygen feature and a LOT of bands on the ship EK80. MOCNESS for fine scale from 480-250. Brilliant. Taking photos of all fish, decapods, and squid over 2 cm. Tucker trawl to midwater to catch the scatter layer for physiology. Respiration started from day Tucker (oldish water). Water containers cleaned and new filtered water on the way. Wireflyer did its thing. EK80 from the ship was having processing issues. Resolved (it was because they were using it to look at the bottom so we could not see the data in the out files). Loki at 2200.

	Trip	RSP	Date	Time	Pres	Net Angle	Flow Cnts	Volume
1	●●	240514	194628	480.2	46.5	260	1816.3	
2	●●	240514	195457	455.1	44.8	89	623.9	
3	●●	240514	195955	435.1	51.1	61	407.8	
4	●●	240514	201053	405.3	53.2	155	1017.7	
5	●●	240514	201813	385.1	47.6	91	610.2	
6	●●	240514	202415	374.1	52.0	65	430.0	
7	●●	240514	203615	330.1	49.6	144	959.2	
8	●●	240514	204528	300.5	48.0	101	685.1	
9	●●	240514	205558	250.1	46.1	107	776.9	
10	●●	240514	211253	-0.1	2.3	210	1332.6	

Net	Avg. oxygen	Min of oxygen	Max of oxygen	Avg. temp	Min temp	Max temp	Min depth	Max depth	Volume Filtered
0	0.785	0.093	4.995	12.54	8.77	25.63	0.9	485	1816.3
1	0.096	0.093	0.101	9.02	8.78	9.21	455.1	480	623.9
2	0.103	0.094	0.124	9.42	9.21	9.72	435.2	455	407.8
3	0.156	0.122	0.174	9.90	9.71	10.06	405.3	435	1017.7
4	0.129	0.122	0.286	10.19	10.05	11.91	263.9	405	610.2
5	0.176	0.128	0.206	10.52	10.30	10.67	374	385	430
6	0.231	0.126	0.274	10.90	10.66	10.98	330.1	374	959.2
7	0.156	0.122	0.206	11.31	10.97	11.60	300.4	330	685.1
8	0.307	0.204	0.415	11.97	11.60	12.27	250.2	300	776.9
9	1.243	0.402	5.373	14.72	12.27	25.28	-0.3	250	1332.6

5/15/2024 (SR2408) – Carmen

Dive successful collected many pneumoderma and cliopsis, one yellow larvacean. Tucker was not talking then it was. Trawl 380-350. Respirations set up with dive and tucker animals (*Pasiphaea pacifica*, pneumoderma). MOC 0-1000 run by Sem and Ro! Beautiful!!!! Half in ethanol for Jamie, half for us in formalin. Two interesting fish in net (750-500). Gave them to Uriel. CTD to bottom with cups. Loki to 300 m. Reeve caught one of the salps that have not been producing FP (during the day) and it made 4 pellets!! Stored. Set up FP experiments for Babbins (euphausiids and copepods). Adorable baby angler fish. Night MOC started stressful as it was not getting any flow counts. We really noticed around 800 m, made the decision to just go to the bottom and see what happened. It worked. Flow counts are comparable to the day tow and Sem and Ro learned important troubleshooting lessons! Got really sharp angle and not enough wire out. Sped up the ship and stopped the winch. Life got better. Sample looks great. Sem and Ro broke down respirations. Hannah saved MANY falcon tubes from both day and night NO for Biomass to Biovolume story.

750-500
m9n2

390-325
m9n4

m9n6 250-100

m9n8 50-25

25-0
m9n9

TRIP CONTROL							
	Trip RSP	Date	Time	Pres	Net Angle Flow Cnts	Volume	
1	●	240515	205518	1000.1	33.5	284	2345.4
2	●	240515	213031	749.9	36.4	278	2224.8
3	●	240515	220134	500.4	42.7	336	2472.9
4	●	240515	221619	389.7	43.2	180	1312.7
5	●	240515	222352	324.4	51.1	92	632.5
6	●	240515	223241	249.4	52.7	117	776.4
7	●	240515	224633	98.9	52.8	200	1359.3
8	●	240515	225019	48.2	48.0	55	375.9
9	●	240515	225214	24.0	50.3	28	191.7
10	●	240515	225448	-0.3	1.0	27	180.8

TRIP CONTROL							
Trip	RSP	Date	Time	Pres	Net Angle Flow Cnts	Volume	
1	●	240516	060942	1000.1	27.5	61	528.1
2	●	240516	064908	750.0	31.6	265	2198.0
3	●	240516	072502	500.2	33.2	328	2663.3
4	●	240516	074052	389.8	30.1	120	1014.7
5	●	240516	074930	325.0	27.9	57	487.9
6	●	240516	075916	249.8	21.5	51	455.2
7	●	240516	082515	99.6	41.4	140	1088.7
8	●	240516	082905	49.2	43.9	38	283.0
9	●	240516	083049	23.8	45.8	22	161.8
10	●	240516	083242	-0.5	31.8	18	136.4

5/16/2024 (SR2408) – Carmen

Tucker to ~400 got pterigioteuthis, salps for respirations. Dive joyful (lots of boat tenders + sea lions). Loki success. Wireflyer having EK80 issues, working to resolve this afternoon. Put in again around 2000, got oxygen and ship EK80 to inform for tomorrow. EK80 still odd. MOCNESS #11 for upper water fine scale (250-0). Last bar did not close properly until the surface so net 9 was empty and net 8 was not quantitative. Deployed MOCNESS #12 to capture the top set of things. Did 75-0, so we have a replicate of the 75-55 nets. Uriel noted that the smaller myctophid species (*Digoenichthys aternatus*) was found more prominently in the upper nets (0-75 in MOC 11, but 0-55 in MOC 12). A second slightly larger myctophid (*Triphoturus mexicanus*) started to be dominant deeper (55-75 in MOC 12 and 75-100 in MOC 11). I need to give him the pictures to explore this more in the deeper MOC 11 nets, but they had already been preserved when he had identified them. All the messed up nets and the 0 are being split

between Uriel and Jamie. Lloyd taking advantage of Reeve time. Going 0-30 then progressively 30 meters deeper to see what he can see! Nothing else to do tonight ☺

5/17/2024 (SR2408) – Carmen

WireFlyer was not functional when they put it in. It appears that there is a nick in the electrical that talks to the clump. They are reterminating. In the meanwhile, the Tucker went in for a 400 m tow (shrimp). Dive (salps). DEEEP Tucker (1800, 1500, 1200). Cool stuff. Much joy. Loki. Wireflyer in the water. Might have seen a big Dosidiucus if both Jake and Lloyd are to be believed.

5/18/2024 (SR2408) – Carmen

WireFlyer did a big U transect all last night. Not much until 6 am. There is a slight feature at ~300 m. We are putting in the MOCNESS to try to follow it. Did the 315 m line. Did not match the wireflyer terribly well, but started at a low oxygen and got increasingly higher. Uriel sees differences in the fish community in the buckets. Will need to see if it correlates to anything. There are some buckets with Pterygioteuthis and some without. Seems like much of this backscatter is pteropod and ostracod?? Might be interesting on the Zooscan. Photographing the big stuff. Tucker went in, towed to 400 m, they got squid and myctophids. LOKI deployed. Broke down the MOC and the Tucker. Hannah started packing up boxes for next year supplies. Washing and hanging nets to dry. Pod of whales. Awesomesauce. Saw their dive under the ship on the echosounder (100m). Wireflyer in at sunset.

Net	Avg. oxygen	Min of oxygen	Max of oxygen	Avg. temp	Min temp	Max temp	Min depth	Max depth	Volume filtered
0	1.001	0.139	4.845	13.97	11.11	25.65	0.0	319.7	546.7
1	0.133	0.108	0.229	11.09	11.06	11.17	314.8	317.5	182.4
2	0.307	0.188	0.384	11.18	11.11	11.23	315.4	317.1	208.8
3	0.280	0.227	0.331	11.07	11.02	11.14	314.4	316.7	220.6
4	0.293	0.254	0.337	11.15	11.07	11.21	314.2	317.0	307.1
5	0.289	0.261	0.444	11.24	11.20	11.34	313.5	315.7	141.7
6	0.467	0.364	0.506	11.38	11.29	11.43	314.6	317.9	220.4
7	0.552	0.499	0.601	11.53	11.43	11.62	312.6	318.2	625.3
8	0.556	0.477	0.613	11.59	11.53	11.64	313.3	316.1	202.1
9	1.389	0.393	5.488	14.19	11.49	25.67	-0.3	316.4	1356.2

TRIP CONTROL							
Trip	RSP	Date	Time	Feet	Net Angle	Flow Cnts	Volume
1	●	240518	182011	315.9	53.1	190	1277.8
2	●	240518	182540	316.1	53.1	56	375.0
3	●	240518	183131	316.5	53.3	64	414.2
4	●	240518	183743	316.7	52.2	67	437.0
5	●	240518	184615	314.6	48.8	94	630.5
6	●	240518	185007	315.7	52.9	42	276.7
7	●	240518	185547	314.7	52.0	65	439.4
8	●	240518	191245	315.8	51.7	186	1271.3
9	●	240518	191801	316.1	51.2	60	398.5
10	●	240518	194745	-0.1	35.9	434	3486.8

5/19/2024 (SR2408) – Carmen

WireFlyer pulled in at 630. Dive at 800, got Cavolinia! Discovered that they renamed Diacria quadridentata to Telodiacria quadridentata in 2019. GRRRR. Got some salps! Loki in after lunch. Reeve in after that (down to 350 mwo). Wireflyer.